

A COMPETENT TEACHER: WAYS OF FORMATION AND MODERN REQUIREMENTS

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Abstract: High-quality education is the key to the development of a country and a civilized society. And the foundation of this knowledge is laid within the walls of the school. Therefore, the most effective way to improve the quality of education is to train competent teachers and create conditions for their professional development. Today's education system is developing in parallel with rapid changes in all spheres of society. The role of the teacher in this process is increasing more than ever. The fact is that a modern student should become not only a learner, but also a critically thinking person, able to sort information, able to make decisions on their own. And for the formation of such a personality, first of all, a competent teacher is needed. The state pays great attention to the field of education, does a lot of work to improve the status of teachers and create a favorable working environment for them. All this makes it possible for a teacher to give a high-quality education and develop himself.

Keywords: education, competence, upbringing, science, innovation, skills, informational, communicative, social, civic, self-development, reflexive, method, approach.

Introduction

Currently, along with the renewal of the education system, the requirements for the teacher's personality are significantly increasing. The 21st century is an era of rapid development of science and technology, when the flow of information becomes a flood. At this time, the future of our country -high-quality education and conscious upbringing of the younger generation -is one of the main tasks of society.

The fulfillment of this task directly depends on the competence of the teacher. Today's teacher is not only a teacher, but also a leading person who reveals the abilities of students, guides, and develops life skills.

Therefore, the concept of a competent teacher is of particular importance in modern pedagogy. High-quality education is the future of the country. High-quality

education is the key to the development of a country and a civilized society. And the foundation of this knowledge is laid within the walls of the school.

Therefore, the most effective way to improve the quality of education is to train competent teachers and create conditions for their professional development. The state pays great attention to the field of education, does a lot of work to improve the status of teachers and create a favorable working environment for them.

All this makes it possible for a teacher to give a high-quality education and develop himself. The relationship between quality education and a competent teacher. High-quality education is the main prerequisite for the development of any society. It is the foundation of scientific achievements, economic growth and cultural progress. And the foundation of this high-quality education is laid within the walls of the school. Therefore, the teacher is the heart, the pillar of the knowledge system.

Results and discussion. A competent teacher contributes not only to the education of students, but also to the development of their logical, critical thinking, and the assimilation of life values. Such a teacher gets to know each student as a person, applying an individual approach to him, sharpens his creative abilities, inspires self-confidence.

For example, in the traditional education system, the teacher acts as a source of information, currently he is a partner, an adviser to the student in the educational process. These partnerships are based on mutual respect, trust and cooperation. In such an environment, students learn to think freely, express their opinions openly, and act creatively.

Today's education system is developing in parallel with rapid changes in all spheres of society. The role of the teacher in this process is increasing more than ever. The fact is that a modern student should become not only a student, but also a critically thinking person, able to sort information, able to make decisions on their own. And for the formation of such a personality, first of all, a competent teacher is needed.

What is competence?

Competence is the ability of a teacher not only to transfer knowledge, but also to effectively transfer it, teach taking into account the specifics of the student, and harmoniously apply methods of education and training. In other words, competence is a set of professional personal qualities of a teacher, including the unity of knowledge, skills and abilities.

Materials and methods. According to the four pillars of education proposed by UNESCO: the skills of "knowing", "being able", "living together" and "being" form the basis of a teacher's competencies. In addition to being an expert in his field, the teacher must be able to recognize the student as a person and create conditions for

his personal development. Competence is not limited to the amount of knowledge, it is directly related to the methodological, communicative, informational and personal development of the teacher. Today, a teacher becomes not only a source of knowledge for a student, but also a guide, consultant, and inspiring personality.

Who is a competent person?

A competent person is a person who is able to effectively apply his knowledge in life, make decisions independently, think critically, be communicative and socially responsible.

Who is a competent teacher?

A competent teacher is not only a specialist who knows the subject, but also a teacher who knows modern pedagogical technologies and is able to work creatively, taking into account the individual characteristics of each student. He is constantly developing his professional skills and putting innovative ideas into practice.

Ways to form a competent teacher

A competent teacher is not a personality that is formed in one day. This is the result of continuous professional development and self-improvement. The following mechanisms are important to ensure the professional development of a teacher:

1. Professional development courses and seminars;
2. exchange of teachers' experience, participation in professional associations;
3. Participation in research work, generalization of own experience;
4. mastering new technologies and techniques;
5. conducting pedagogical reflection and self-assessment.

The teacher must improve his knowledge and master new directions in accordance with the constantly changing demands of the time. This must have been the origin of the saying, "A teacher is an eternal student."

The main directions of a competent teacher:

1. subject competence -deep knowledge of one's subject and its presentation in an interesting, accessible form corresponding to the student's level;
2. methodological competence-mastery of various teaching methods, effective use of new pedagogical technologies;
3. Information competence-digital literacy, effective use of ICT tools in the classroom;
4. Communicative competence-the ability to communicate effectively with students, parents and colleagues;
5. Reflexive competence is the ability to critically approach one's activities, differentiate between achievements and shortcomings, and plan areas of professional development.

The results of the study. The main qualities of a competent teacher:

1. professional knowledge and skills-deep knowledge of the content of the subject, the ability to present it in an understandable and interesting way;
2. mastering a wide range of pedagogical techniques-recognizing the student as a person and learning in various ways;
3. innovation-application of digital technologies, continuous professional development;
4. Communication skills-the ability to communicate effectively with students, parents, and colleagues;
5. responsibility and commitment – honesty in your business, responsible attitude to the quality of knowledge.

Ways to form a competent teacher			
№	Ways of formation, direction	Content	Comments
1	Advanced training courses	The training aimed at mastering modern pedagogical technologies and techniques ensures the professional education of teachers, the development of new	Advanced training courses for teachers at the NCPC "Orleu". Training on the "updated content of education". Participation in trainings on STEM and CLIL methods

		methods and programs.	
2	Exchange of experience	Improving pedagogical skills by conducting open classes with colleagues, participating in master classes, mutual coaching, and sharing experiences with colleagues	Conducting open lessons and attending classes. Intra-school workshops. Conducting a joint study using the "Lesson Study" method
3	Participation in professional associations	Adoption of best practices through educational forums, online/offline communities. Promotes mutual cooperation of teachers, assimilation of the best pedagogical experience	Republican and regional pedagogical associations. Teacher groups on Facebook, Telegram. Participation in professional forums such as EdCamp, QazTED
4	Self-education	Reading specialized literature, reviewing scientific articles, participating in webinars and online courses. Improving the teacher's knowledge through independent search	Reading books on pedagogy, psychology, methodology. Take online courses on the platforms Coursera, Khan Academy, Bilimland. Reading articles related to the profession
5	Participation in research work	To conduct a scientific analysis of their teaching experience and improve it	Study of the problem in the lesson process (action research). Participation in creative competitions of teachers. Publication of scientific articles (for example: "education", "teacher", "Әдістеме.kz")
6	Knowledge of information and communication technologies	Improving the quality of training through the use of digital tools	Using Google Classroom, Zoom, Padlet, Kahoot, Quizizz. Digital test, online training. Preparation of

			interactive presentations and video tutorials
7	Reflection and self-assessment	Analyzing the results of their activities, identifying strengths and weaknesses	Filling out the reflection sheet after the lesson. Keeping a diary "My successes and mistakes". Development of an individual development plan (PD Plan
8	Maintaining psychological and emotional stability	Prevention of professional burnout, maintenance of internal motivation, development of emotional intelligence	Team building, collective events. Stress management trainings. Maintaining inner balance through physical activity, meditation, hobbies (reading, drawing, traveling)

This table contains the main directions that ensure the comprehensive development of a competent teacher.

Conclusion. To summarize, we come to the concept that a competent teacher is the key to quality education. A competent teacher is the key to the future of the nation. He is a person who knows how to find a way to the heart of a student, is dedicated to his work, and develops with society. Only such teachers can educate a conscious and educated generation that will make the future of our country brighter. Therefore, the main task on the way to improving the quality of education is to increase the competence of each teacher, support his professional development and strengthen his status in society.

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